

GENRES , STYLES AND TYPES OF FINE ART: DEFINITIONS AND METHODS

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Annotation

Many different types, styles, genres and trends in visual art. In addition, one genre often gives rise to subgenres, styles - new directions of painting, and the methods used by artists remain mixed and ambiguous. In this article, we will try to continuously reveal the main features of this topic.

Keywords: Art, genre, type, color, graphics, sculpture, technique, painting, paint.

Fine art is artistic creativity in general, i.e. a general class of spatial art that combines the following six popular creative directions : painting , sculpture , graphics . Descriptive name main the purpose is the author's himself manifestation to do and to the viewer emotional effect is to show . And if there is a goal , there are quality signs that can recognize it in the surrounding world , namely:

- **Sensuality** - works of art are created and perceived through them.
- **The image - a form of knowledge of the world** - is transmitted in the form of clear images that are understandable to the viewer, and sometimes, on the contrary, are hidden from the observer .

- **Subjectivity** is the author's individual view of the current reality.
- **Completeness** - the presence of a finished composition, completion of work.
- **Exclusivity** - a **unique** original that is difficult to duplicate or has no value .

Thus, all types of visual arts visually reproduce the objectively existing qualities of the real world : volume, colors, space, material form of objects, light and air environment. For visual arts, there is not only the recording of an image, but also the temporal development of events, a more or less developed story, dynamic movement, as well as the expression of subjective experiences, fantasies and abstract ideas .

Types of Fine Art- We've discussed what fine art is, but how do the types differ? One of the most important criteria for their correct final determination is size. It is often called three-dimensional or planar . To be clear, it is volume that determines the difference between painting and sculpture, the two main types of fine art that developed in the distant past .

Painting is the art of drawing with paints on a flat two - dimensional surface

- **Graphics** - working with lines on a plane without using paints .
- **Sculpture** is a three - dimensional creation made by carving, sculpting and casting .

Painting is a form of visual art that is a method of conveying visual images by applying paint to a two -dimensional surface . This method allows the artist to photograph the world around him or his fantasies, which will then be open to the viewer . His main means of expression is color, which affects the viewer's general

perception of the picture, allows to pay attention to some details and increases the emotional part of the work. For this, the artist often mixes colors on the palette and uses expressive shades, tones and shades necessary to clearly convey the idea. In addition to color, the most popular methods of artistic expression in painting include: drawing composition . The result is the final image taken on a certain surface chosen by the author as a basis . According to the execution technique , objects are divided into paintings, frescoes, icons, rock paintings and miniatures .

claims to be the oldest form of art . It has evolved over many centuries from rock paintings of the Paleolithic era to the latest trends of the 21st century. It appeared almost with the appearance of mankind . Ancient people painted everything they saw around them: tribesmen, animals, nature and hunting scenes . For painting , they used primitive paints made from available natural materials . These were earth paints , charcoal , black soot, plant extracts and mud. Brushes are made of animal hair or they are simply painted with fingers .

Throughout history, the methods of painting and the materials they use have been constantly changing . New technologies and changing tastes have led to the constant improvement of paints and painting methods used by artists . Most of us are familiar with watercolors, oils and acrylics, but artists use a much wider range. Some painting techniques are easy to learn for artists of all skill levels , while others may require more advanced technical skills .

a certain sequence and set of techniques for the use of artistic materials and tools in the preparation of works of art . The following techniques are available:

Watercolor - Usually painted on paper using pigments suspended in a water-based solution . Watercolor paint, known for its transparent layers, dissolves even after drying . This means that artists can make some changes even when the painting

is dry, but it means that the finished work must be carefully protected from external factors. There are many watercolor techniques that artists use to create a variety of art styles, from realistic portraits to blurred landscapes . Although paper is the most common medium , watercolor can also be used on surfaces such as fabric, wood, leather, and parchment.

Watercolor - For centuries, artists have used oil paints to create their best works . This slow-drying medium consists of color pigments suspended in oil. Since the drying time is long , you can take your time with work. Oil paints are often used to create great textural effects due to their thick consistency. Although it can be messy to work with and requires caution when working with environments containing toxic elements, it is still loved by artisans for the rich colors it produces. Therefore, it is not surprising that it is one of the most popular types of painting.

Acrylic - Acrylic paints come in a wide variety of textures and drying times. This waterborne paint dries quickly, is non-toxic and cost-effective, often making it the preferred choice for artists of all skill levels. It holds up better than oil paint over time because it doesn't crack or yellow. There are countless acrylic painting techniques, and by combining paint with different mediums, artists gain flexibility in the final look. While acrylic is water-resistant once fully dry on the canvas, its water solubility when wet makes it difficult to clean. **Gouache** - Gouache to watercolor it 's similar if - though , him again moisten possible though - this kind of paint mat the color dries and contained chalk because of heavy iron will be SHE IS often watercolors with together is used and she is in the water dissolves because ready the picture to close for his on top of it lacquer need new option acrylic gouache be ,

he paint when dry to water resistant to be possibility giver acrylic justified from the linker uses

Pastel – Sometimes known as "dry painting", the use of pastel has been popular since the 16th century. Their stick shape and no drying time make them an easy and portable solution for artists. The most popular pastels, known as soft pastels, contain chalk, but there are also oil pastels with a waxy consistency. These paintings are fragile because the pigment can peel off the surface, so they must be framed under glass.

Enamel - This oil paint is often used by gesture artists or for decorative painting and line drawing. After drying, it forms a hard, glossy, weather-resistant surface. Enamel can be used on a variety of surfaces such as glass, ceramic, metal, wood and canvas. Due to its toxicity, it is always recommended to wear a mask when working in a well-ventilated area. There are also water-based enamels that can be used on thicker papers such as cardstock. Many fine artists used enamels in their works in addition to decorative work and gesture painting. Picasso and Jackson Pollack are known to have used commercial enamel paints in their work.

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